

THE COMPILATION OF MAGAZINES AS A MEDIUM FOR STUDENT CREATIVITY IN JOURNALISM EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the potential for student creativity through journalism extracurricular activities with a focus on preparing magazines as a medium of expression and learning. The preparation of magazines is not only considered as a final result that can be consumed by the school community, but also as a learning process that involves students in developing writing, photography and graphic design skills. Implementation methods include selecting relevant themes, forming an editorial team, skills training, distributing tasks to each division, and collecting material through research and interviews.

Keywords: *Students, Extracurricular Journalism, Magazines*

I. INTRODUCTION

The dynamics of modern education and the development of students' potential are not limited to the classroom but also involve activities outside the formal curriculum. The journalism extracurricular activity is a platform that enables students to enhance their productivity by channeling their interests in writing, gathering information, and collaborating in delivering news. The school magazine, as a new product of the extracurricular activity, is not just a collection of writings but also reflects the high creativity, dedication, and collaborative spirit of the students. In this article, we will explore the role of magazine creation as a medium for student creativity within the journalism extracurricular activity. This process not only serves as a platform for the development of journalistic skills but also enriches students' experiences in collaborating to create a school identity and disseminate information effectively.

Education is not only confined to classroom learning but also involves extracurricular activities as a means to develop students' potential and creativity. One extracurricular activity that can provide valuable experience is journalism. In this context, the creation of a school magazine becomes an intriguing activity to explore.

A magazine not only provides a platform for expressing ideas and opinions but also encourages students to hone their skills in writing, editing, and graphic design. This article will discuss the methods of implementing magazine creation as a medium for student creativity in journalism extracurricular activities.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methods used in carrying out teaching assistance activities at SMA N 1 Kamal are in the form of mentoring students in the journalism extracurricular program. The stages of the activities carried out are as follows:

1. **Theme Selection:** Choosing the central theme that will guide the content and focus of the magazine.
2. **Editorial Team Formation:** Organizing students into an editorial team, assigning roles such as editors, writers, and designers.
3. **Skill Training:** Providing training sessions to enhance students' skills in writing, editing, and graphic design.
4. **Division of Tasks:** Assigning specific tasks to each division within the editorial team, ensuring that all aspects of magazine production are covered.
5. **Material Collection:** Gathering all necessary materials, including articles, images, and graphics, for inclusion in the magazine.

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The implementation of the magazine creation work program begins with consultations with the supervising teachers and extracurricular advisors. The process of the activity begins with five stages, as follows:

3.1 Theme Selection

The process of creating the school magazine, "Jurnalisa," begins with the critical step of selecting a theme that resonates with the students and the school community. The chosen theme serves as the backbone of the magazine, influencing not only its title but also the content and overall tone. A relevant and engaging theme ensures that students are motivated to contribute actively, making the production process both meaningful and enjoyable.

In determining the theme, collaboration is key. The assistant team, journalism extracurricular students, and the supervising teacher work together to identify a theme that captures the spirit of the school and reflects current issues, school life, or specific student interests. This collaborative approach leads to the selection of the school magazine's title, "Jurnalisa," with the fitting tagline, "Jurnalistik Smansaka," which encapsulates the essence of the journalistic endeavors at the school.

The theme selection process extends beyond just choosing a title; it also involves deciding on the sections and content to be included in the magazine. This careful consideration resulted in the establishment of six official content sections for "Jurnalisa," each serving a unique purpose in showcasing different aspects of school life:

- **Galeria Smansaka:** This section features the school's profile, emphasizing its achievements and cultural heritage. It provides readers with an in-depth understanding of what makes the school unique.
- **Kilas Ekstrakurikuler:** A dedicated space to cover the various extracurricular activities offered at the school, highlighting student involvement and the diversity of options available to them.
- **Performa Siswa:** Showcasing student achievements and success stories, this section aims to inspire and motivate other students by celebrating the accomplishments of their peers.
- **Aksi P5:** This segment highlights student projects and initiatives, particularly those that align with the school's educational framework and values.
- **Festival Istimewa:** Reporting on the celebration of significant holidays and special events at the school, this section brings the vibrancy of school life to the forefront.

By carefully selecting a theme and organizing the magazine into these sections, "Jurnalisa" ensures that its content is not only diverse and engaging but also reflective of the students' interests and the school's identity. This thoughtful approach helps create a publication that resonates deeply with the entire school community.

3.2 Formation of the Editorial Team

The formation of the editorial team is a crucial step in the magazine production process, designed to align with students' individual interests and strengths. This tailored approach not only ensures that tasks are executed efficiently but also fosters a sense of ownership and enthusiasm among the students. The editorial team is structured as follows:

- **Editor-in-Chief:** This role is central to the entire magazine production process. The Editor-in-Chief is responsible for overseeing all activities, ensuring that the magazine's vision is maintained, and that all sections are cohesive and of high quality.
- **Managing Editor:** Acting as the right hand of the Editor-in-Chief, the Managing Editor is tasked with coordinating the schedule for content collection and production. This role involves assisting in editorial decisions and ensuring that deadlines are met.
- **Reporter:** Reporters are the eyes and ears of the magazine. They are responsible for covering events, conducting interviews, and gathering all the necessary information that will be transformed into articles. Their work is fundamental to the magazine's content.
- **Photographer:** The Photographer's role is to capture compelling images that complement the written content. These images bring life to the stories and add a visual dimension to the magazine's narrative.
- **Creative Team:** This group is responsible for the visual and artistic aspects of the magazine. They design the layout, create graphics, and ensure that the magazine is visually appealing. They also write descriptions and captions for the images and activities covered.

- **Layout Designer:** Working closely with the Creative Team, the Layout Designer edits and finalizes the magazine's layout. This role requires attention to detail and an understanding of design principles to ensure that the magazine is both readable and aesthetically pleasing.

To prepare the students for their roles, the teaching assistants provide targeted training sessions. Reporters receive instruction on journalistic techniques, including how to conduct interviews and write compelling stories. Photographers are trained in camera use, focusing on how to effectively capture images that enhance the magazine's content. This training equips students with the necessary skills to perform their duties confidently and competently.

Once the team is trained, tasks are divided among the various divisions. Each division has a designated leader responsible for overseeing the completion of specific tasks. This division of labor ensures that the content material is gathered efficiently and that each aspect of the magazine's production is handled by the appropriate team members. This organized approach facilitates smooth workflow and effective collaboration.

The collection of content material is a critical phase of the production process, scheduled for completion by the end of November. During this period, reporters gather stories, photographers capture images, and the Creative Team begins conceptualizing the magazine's design. Once the content is collected, it is handed over to the Creative Team, who compile and organize it into the final magazine format.

The process of creating a school magazine within the journalism extracurricular activity extends beyond the production of a tangible product. It is a comprehensive educational experience that fosters personal development in numerous ways. Through their involvement, students enhance their ability to express themselves creatively, improve their communication skills, and develop a deeper sense of responsibility and discipline. Teamwork is also emphasized, as students must collaborate effectively to produce a cohesive final product.

The creation of the magazine offers long-term benefits by providing students with valuable experiences that contribute to their growth as individuals. It allows them to explore the world of journalism and media in a practical, hands-on environment, which can be both motivating and inspiring. By the end of the process, students not only take pride in the final magazine but also in the skills and lessons they have learned along the way. This experience serves as a powerful tool for student engagement and development, equipping them with skills that will be valuable in their future academic and professional endeavors.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The work program for magazine creation began with consultations with the supervising teacher and extracurricular advisor. This process involved five main stages:

1. **Theme Selection:** The theme was chosen by considering its relevance and appeal to students. The collaboration between the assistant team, extracurricular students, and the supervising teacher led to the selection of

the theme "Jurnalisa" with the tagline "Jurnalistik Smansaka." The theme selection not only covered the magazine's title but also the content, including six official sections such as Galeri Smansaka, Kilas Ekstrakurikuler, Performa Siswa, Aksi P5, and Festival Istimewa.

2. Editorial Team Formation: The editorial team was formed based on students' interests to ensure ease in carrying out the magazine's content-related tasks. The editorial team involved roles such as Editor-in-Chief, Managing Editor, Reporter, Photographer, Creative Team, and Layout Designer.
3. Skill Training: The teaching assistance students provided training, including how to be a good and proper reporter as well as training in using cameras to capture content material.
4. Task Division by Division

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